

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KOTTAM****FIRST NAME: VAMSHI KRISHNA REDDY****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0% (excluding content in the template and Bibliography)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in the text, then bold these terms in your RP:

1. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6)
2. Good research question (Turabian 2018, 24)
3. End notes and footnotes (Turabian 2018, 160)
4. Research proposal (Bloomberg and Volpe 2018, 17 – 18)
5. Ideal recommendation (Bloomberg and Volpe 2018, 158)

QUIZ

1. How do we avoid Plagiarism?

- Cite the author or source that has provided the information¹**
- Paraphrase the sentences from the source and ignore the citation
- Use more periods to break the sentence
- Use quotation marks for the subject of the sentence

¹Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 6.

2. **When do we have to place a comma before “and” while writing a sentence?**

- When combining two different sentences
- When describing a list of items²**
- When there are no other conjunctions in the sentence
- When the sentence starts with a lowercase letter

3. **A good research question is one that:**

- Is worth answering.
- Adds value to the field of research.
- Is not vague.
- All of the above.³**

4. **Writer’s block can be addressed by:**

- Creating a routine and avoiding any distractions.⁴**
- Doing nothing.
- Getting distracted often.
- Setting high and non-achievable goals.

² Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma, 19-20.

³ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 24.

⁴ Kate L Turabian, 83.

5. **The easiest way to differentiate a journal article from a magazine article is to check if the:**

- The author has used citations.⁵**
- The website it is published on is reputed.
- The article has a lot of opinions.
- The article has an introduction and conclusion.

6. **When should we use End notes instead of footnotes?**

- If the number of references is more.⁶**
- If the number of references is less.
- If the page is long.
- If the citation does not have an author name.

7. **While working on a thesis dissertation, the next step after finalizing the research topic is to**

- develop a proposal.⁷**
- conduct literature review.
- collect data.
- present the analysis.

⁵ Kate L Turabian, 262.

⁶ Kate L Turabian, 160.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. (Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, 2018), 17-18.

8. **At what stage of writing a thesis dissertation does a researcher evaluates, analyses, and synthesizes the research information?**

- While drawing the conclusions⁸**
- While identifying a research topic
- While running quantitative tests on data
- While presenting the literature review

9. **An ideal recommendation presented at the end of a study is one that**

- is not aligned with the conclusions drawn from the research.
- is based on the author's bias.
- is very elaborate and difficult to implement.
- leaves no room for speculation.⁹**

10. **In which year was the Maastricht treaty signed to establish the European Union?**

- 1992¹⁰**
- 2002
- 1987
- 2001

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 156.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 158.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2016), 74.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.